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Booklet

MINI-RESEARCH PROJECT

A Practical Guide

2021

Biology Education Program
Faculty of Teacher Training and Education
University of Palangka Raya

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Biology Education Program
University of Palangka Raya
Palangka Raya
Indonesia

Booklet

MINI-RESEARCH PROJECT A Practical Guide

Based on the research:

Haryono, A., & Adam, C. (2021). The Implementation of Mini-Research Project to Train Undergraduate Students' Scientific Writing and Communication Skills. *Journal of Biological Education Indonesia (Jurnal Pendidikan Biologi Indonesia)*, 7(2), 159-170. DOI: [10.22219/jpbi.v7i2.15838](https://doi.org/10.22219/jpbi.v7i2.15838)

MRP Official Website:

<http://miniresearch.website2.me/>

Cover Image:
Mini-Research Project Documentation
(Original Author Archive)

Preface

This booklet provides the description of the Mini-Research Project (MRP), the learning method that was developed for undergraduate students based on the research that was conducted in the Biology Education Program, University of Palangka Raya. Hopefully, this booklet can be used both as a reference and a guide to implementing the Mini-Research Project (MRP) in the learning activities.

Regards,

Prof. Dr. Agus Haryono, M.Si.
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Introduction

About Mini-Research Project

The Mini-Research Project (MRP) is a form of research project-based learning designed for lecture activities at the Biology Education Study Program, University of Palangka Raya. Through MRP activities, students are given the opportunity to carry out their research projects independently, so that the learning process becomes student-oriented (Student-Centered Learning).

Submission of Mini-Research project reports is simulated like the procedure for submitting article manuscripts to scientific journals. Mini-Research reports are written in the form of scientific articles with minimum requirements and predetermined templates. With this, students are trained to be able to develop scientific writing skills independently.

Students' Feedback on MRP

The survey results showed that the implementation of Mini-Research received good feedback from students and they suggested that it be implemented in other courses as well (Haryono & Adam, 2021). Table 1 shows the students' feedback in detail.

Table 1. Students' Feedback on the Mini-Research Implementation

No.	Question(s)	Feedback
1	Are you satisfied with the Mini-Research Implementation in Animal Ecology field practice?	60% (Very Satisfied) 29% (Satisfied) 10% (Neutral) 2% (Unsatisfied) Figure 7

No.	Question(s)	Feedback
2	Did you acquire new knowledge and skills in scientific writing through this Mini-Research activity?	98% (Yes) 2% (No)
3	Regarding question number 2, how significant is it?	58% (Very Significant) 38% (Significant) 4% (Neutral)
4	What knowledge/Skills did you acquire?	Plagiarism 63.6% Abstract 77.3% Introduction 65.9% Methods 63.6% Results (Data Presentation) 61.4% Discussion 61.4% Citation and Reference 75%
5	Describe the benefits you get from Mini-Research?	a. Gain new practical field experience that is different from previous practices. b. acquire knowledge about how to write good scientific papers. c. know the importance of avoiding plagiarism in scientific writing. d. develop scientific writing skills and

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No.	Question(s)	Feedback
		<p>interpret research results well.</p> <p>e. obtain an overview of how to plan and conduct research, and how to process data and report it in the form of scientific papers.</p> <p>f. helps make it easier to understand the concepts in animal ecology courses.</p>
6	Describe the obstacles when you did Animal Ecology field practice activities with Mini-Research?	Outdoor practical field activities are limited due to the COVID-19 pandemic.
7	Does this Mini-Research need to be implemented in other courses?	98% (Yes) 2% (No)

Source: [Haryono & Adam \(2021\)](#)

Fig. 1. Students' Satisfaction

"Students gain practical field experience that makes them feel like they are doing research. Through this mini-research they are trained to plan and conduct research and communicate the results independently. Students gained precious knowledge about the importance of avoiding plagiarism in scientific writing and developed skills in scientific writing and research results interpretation." – A. Haryono & C. Adam (2021)

MRP Official Website

The MRP website was created and developed to provide information about the Mini-Research Project (MRP) that can be easily accessed online and to facilitate the publication of student project reports.

The MRP website can be accessed by the following URL:

The information that provided on the MRP website are:

1. About Mini-Research Project (MRP) including: General Description, Technical Implementation, Mini-Research Reports Template;
2. The collection of student final project reports;
3. Documentation; and
4. Announcements.

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Fig. 2. MRP Website Homepage

MINI-RESEARCH PROJECT

The screenshot displays the 'MINI-RESEARCH PROJECT' website. The navigation bar includes 'Home', 'About', 'MRP Reports', 'Galleries', 'Blog', and 'Contact'. The main header identifies the 'Biology Education Program' at the 'University of Palanghara Raya'. A language selection tool is visible, powered by Google Translate. The central area features a carousel of report covers with the following titles and actions:

- Animal Ecology Vol. 1: Download
- Environmental Science Vol. 1: Download
- Invertebrate Zoology Vol. 1: Download
- Animal Ecology Vol. 2: Coming Soon
- Plant Ecology Vol. 1: Coming Soon
- Learning Media Development Vol. 1 No. 1: Coming Soon
- Learning Media Development Vol. 1 No. 2: Coming Soon

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Fig. 3. The Collection of Student Final Project Reports

The screenshot displays the 'MINI-RESEARCH PROJECT' website, specifically the 'Galleries' section. The navigation bar is consistent with the previous image. The main header identifies the 'Biology Education Program' at the 'University of Palanghara Raya'. A language selection tool is visible, powered by Google Translate. The central area is titled 'Invertebrate Zoology' and is divided into three columns of documentation:

- Sampling:** Shows students in a field setting, likely collecting samples.
- Laboratory Observation:** Shows students in a laboratory setting, using microscopes.
- Presentation:** Shows a virtual meeting or presentation screen with multiple participants.

Below the images are three sets of dots indicating a carousel or gallery view.

Fig. 4. MRP Documentation

Technical Implementation of MINI-RESEARCH PROJECT

Technical Implementation

The implementation of the Mini-Research Project consists of 5 (five) stages, i.e., Design, Propose, Execute, Present, and Report.

Design

Each group of students designs a Research Project based on a given topic. The design of the Mini-Research Project includes Title, Objectives, and Methods.

Propose

Presentation of the Mini-Research Project Design to be discussed in a forum facilitated by the course lecturer.

Execute

The design of the Mini-Research Project which has been discussed and approved by the Lecturer is then carried out by each group.

Present

At this stage, each group of students presents the results of their Mini-Research Project.

Report

Preparation of Mini-Research Project reports according to a predetermined template.

Fig. 2. DPEPR: The 5 Stages of Mini-Research Project

Mini-Research Project Reports

The Mini-Research report is written in the form of a scientific article with minimum requirements and a predetermined

template. The minimum requirements for accepted Mini-Research Project reports are as follows:

- a. According to the Template; and
- b. Has a similarity index $\leq 20\%$.

Submission of Mini-Research project reports is simulated like the procedure for submitting article manuscripts to scientific journals. Mini-Research reports are written in the form of scientific articles with minimum requirements and predetermined templates. With this, students are trained to be able to develop scientific writing skills independently.

Fig. 3. Mini-Research Project Reports Submission

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Fig. 4. Example of Mini-Research Project Report Template

Reference

Haryono, A., & Adam, C. (2021). The implementation of mini-research project to train undergraduate students' scientific writing and communication skills. *JPBI (Jurnal Pendidikan Biologi Indonesia)*, 7(2), 159–170. <https://doi.org/10.22219/jpbi.v7i2.15838>

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Kewarganegaraan : Indonesia

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Judul Ciptaan : **Mini-Research Project: A Practical Guide**
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